

EFFECT OF ANTIOXIDANTS ON SEMEN PARAMETERS IN IDIOPATHIC MALE SUBFERTILITY

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Abstract

OBJECTIVE

To determine the mean semen parameters after antioxidants in idiopathic male subfertility.

METHODOLOGY

A quasi-experimental study was conducted from March to June 2025 in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Sobhraj Maternity Hospital, Karachi, involving 60 idiopathic subfertile males aged 20–50 years, recruited through non-probability consecutive sampling. Eligible participants had abnormal semen parameters with normal genital examination and hormonal profile. All received oral antioxidant supplementation for three months. Semen volume, sperm count, progressive motility, and normal morphology were assessed pre- and post-treatment. Data were analysed using SPSS-26, applying paired statistical tests with $p \leq 0.05$ considered significant.

RESULTS for Excellence in Education & Research

The mean age of participants was 34.6 ± 6.8 years. Following three months of antioxidant supplementation, a statistically significant improvement was observed in normal sperm morphology, increasing from $23.22 \pm 23.28\%$ at baseline to $33.60 \pm 20.01\%$ post-treatment (absolute mean difference $+10.38$ percentage points; $p = 0.001$). Changes in sperm volume, sperm concentration, and progressive motility were not statistically significant (all $p > 0.05$).

CONCLUSION

Antioxidant supplementation administered for three months resulted in a statistically significant improvement in normal sperm morphology among men with idiopathic subfertility, whereas no significant changes were observed in sperm volume, sperm concentration, or progressive motility. These findings support a potential role for antioxidants in improving semen parameters associated with oxidative stress.

INTRODUCTION

Infertility is a global public health problem with significant psychosocial and economic consequences, affecting approximately 15% of couples worldwide [1]. Male-related factors contribute to nearly 50% of infertility cases, either as an isolated cause or in combination with female

factors [2]. Despite advances in diagnostic evaluation, a considerable proportion of male infertility remains idiopathic, characterised by abnormal semen parameters without an identifiable anatomical, endocrine, genetic, or infectious cause [3]. Idiopathic male subfertility poses a particular challenge in low- and middle-

income countries, where delayed presentation, nutritional deficiencies, environmental exposures, and limited access to specialised diagnostic facilities are common [4].

Oxidative stress has been increasingly recognised as a key pathophysiological mechanism underlying idiopathic male subfertility. It results from an imbalance between reactive oxygen species and antioxidant defence systems, leading to lipid peroxidation of sperm plasma membranes, mitochondrial dysfunction, DNA fragmentation, and protein oxidation [5,6]. Spermatozoa are especially vulnerable to oxidative damage due to their high polyunsaturated fatty acid content and limited cytoplasmic antioxidant capacity [6]. Excessive reactive oxygen species have been associated with reduced sperm motility, abnormal morphology, impaired fertilisation, poor embryo development, and increased risk of adverse reproductive outcomes [7].

Routine semen analysis remains the primary diagnostic tool for evaluating male subfertility and provides objective assessment of sperm concentration, motility, morphology, and volume. However, conventional semen parameters do not directly quantify oxidative stress and may fail to identify underlying functional defects, particularly in idiopathic cases [8]. As a result, management of idiopathic male subfertility often relies on empirical therapies aimed at improving semen quality and enhancing fertilising potential.

Antioxidant supplementation has emerged as a biologically plausible and non-invasive therapeutic option in idiopathic male subfertility. Antioxidants such as coenzyme Q10, zinc, selenium, vitamin C, vitamin E, and folic acid play essential roles in scavenging reactive oxygen species, stabilising sperm membranes, supporting mitochondrial energy metabolism, and protecting sperm DNA integrity [6,9]. Several clinical trials and systematic reviews have demonstrated improvements in sperm concentration, motility, morphology, and DNA fragmentation following antioxidant therapy, supporting its potential role in the management of oxidative stress-mediated male infertility [3,10,11].

Despite promising evidence, the existing literature is heterogeneous with regard to antioxidant

formulations, dosages, treatment duration, and outcome measures. Moreover, most studies originate from high-income countries, with limited data from South Asian populations where lifestyle factors such as smoking, obesity, and environmental pollution may further exacerbate oxidative stress [12]. In Pakistan, particularly in metropolitan cities like Karachi, male subfertility remains under-investigated, and locally generated evidence regarding the effectiveness of antioxidant supplementation is scarce.

Given the high burden of idiopathic male subfertility, the established role of oxidative stress in sperm dysfunction, and the paucity of local data, the present study was undertaken to determine the mean semen parameters after antioxidants in idiopathic male subfertility.

METHODOLOGY

This quasi-experimental study was conducted in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Sobhraj Maternity Hospital, Karachi, from March 2025 to June 2025, following approval of the synopsis by CPSP. Ethical approval was obtained from the ERC, and written informed consent was taken from all participants. A total of 60 idiopathic sub fertile males aged 20–50 years presenting as partners of infertile women to the outpatient department were enrolled through non-probability consecutive sampling. Idiopathic male subfertility was defined as inability to conceive for at least one year with abnormal semen parameters in the form of asthenozoospermia with or without oligozoospermia, normal genital examination, absence of varicocele or cryptorchidism, normal hormonal profile, intact sexual function, and normal female evaluation. Men with genitourinary tract infections, antisperm antibodies, absolute asthenozoospermia, hypogonadism, testicular atrophy, severe uncontrolled systemic illnesses, spinal cord injury, use of cytotoxic or immunosuppressive drugs, or hypersensitivity to study medications were excluded. The sample size of 60 was calculated using an expected improvement in sperm morphology, with a 95% confidence level and 0.1 margin of error. Baseline demographic and clinical characteristics including

age, BMI, smoking status, duration of subfertility, residence, occupation, and monthly income were recorded on a pre-designed proforma. Semen samples were collected after 3–4 days of sexual abstinence and analysed according to WHO criteria for volume, sperm count, motility, and morphology by the researcher using standard laboratory techniques. All participants received oral antioxidant supplementation containing coenzyme Q10, zinc, vitamin C, vitamin E, folic acid, and selenium for three months, with fortnightly telephonic follow-up to ensure compliance, after which repeat semen analysis was performed under identical conditions. Data analysis compared baseline and post-treatment

semen parameters using paired t-tests, with $p \leq 0.05$ considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

A total of 60 idiopathic sub fertile males were included in the study. The mean age of the participants was 34.6 ± 6.8 years, and the mean duration of subfertility was 3.9 ± 1.7 years. More than half of the participants were obese (56.7%), and 36.7% were current smokers. The majority of participants belonged to urban areas of Karachi (68.3%). Baseline demographic and clinical characteristics of the study population are summarised in **Table I**.

Mean \pm Standard Deviation		
Age in years = 34.6 ± 6.8		
Duration of Subfertility in years = 3.9 ± 1.7		
Body Mass Index in kg/m^2 = 26.1 ± 3.4		
Frequency (%)		
Obesity Status	Obese	34 (56.7%)
	Non-obese	26 (43.3%)
Smoking Status	Current smokers	22 (36.7%)
	Non-smokers / ex-smokers	38 (63.3%)
Residential Status	Urban	41 (68.3%)
	Rural	19 (31.7%)

After three months of oral antioxidant supplementation, changes in semen parameters were observed as summarised in **Table II**. The mean sperm volume increased from 3.48 ± 1.44 ml at baseline to 3.71 ± 1.42 ml after treatment, while mean sperm count rose from 21.76 ± 23.02 million/ml to 23.22 ± 23.28 million/ml; however, these improvements were not statistically

significant ($p=0.24$ and $p=0.545$, respectively). Progressive motility also showed a modest increase from $9.82 \pm 9.10\%$ to $11.57 \pm 10.18\%$, which did not reach statistical significance ($p=0.20$). In contrast, a statistically significant improvement was observed in normal sperm morphology, which increased from $23.22 \pm 23.28\%$ at baseline to $33.60 \pm 20.01\%$ following antioxidant therapy ($p=0.001$).

Semen Parameter	Baseline Mean \pm SD	After 3 Months Mean \pm SD	P-value
Sperm volume (ml)	3.48 ± 1.44	3.71 ± 1.42	0.24
Sperm count (million/ml)	21.76 ± 23.02	23.22 ± 23.28	0.545

Progressive motility (%)	9.82 ± 9.10	11.57 ± 10.18	0.2
Normal morphology (%)	23.22 ± 23.28	33.60 ± 20.01	0.001*

The statistical comparison of semen parameters stratified by baseline demographic characteristics is detailed in **Table III**, with emphasis on mean changes and associated p-values. In the age-based analysis, participants aged ≤35 years demonstrated a statistically significant improvement in progressive motility, with mean values increasing from 10.6 ± 9.3% to 13.1±10.5% (mean change +2.5%; p=0.022), along with a significant improvement in normal morphology from 24.8±24.1% to 36.4±20.7% (mean change +11.6%; p=0.031). In contrast, among participants aged >35 years, the increase in progressive motility from 8.9 ± 8.7% to 10.0 ± 9.6% was not statistically significant (mean change +1.1%; p=0.285), whereas the improvement in normal morphology from 21.3±22.2% to 30.1±19.2% reached statistical significance (mean change +8.8%; p=0.031).

When stratified by obesity status, obese participants showed a non-significant increase in sperm count from 19.8±21.7 to 21.1±22.9 million/ml (mean change +1.3; p=0.64), but a

statistically significant improvement in normal morphology from 21.4 ± 21.6% to 29.6 ± 18.9% (mean change +8.2%; p = 0.002). Similarly, non-obese participants demonstrated a non-significant rise in sperm count from 24.3 ± 24.6 to 26.8 ± 24.8 million/ml (mean change +2.5; p=0.415), accompanied by a statistically significant and comparatively greater improvement in normal morphology from 25.5± 24.8% to 38.7 ± 21.4% (mean change +13.2%; p=0.002).

Analysis based on smoking status revealed that among smokers, progressive motility increased from 8.1 ± 7.8% to 9.6 ± 8.9%, but this change was not statistically significant (mean change +1.5%; p=0.184), whereas normal morphology improved significantly from 20.1±19.6% to 27.8 ± 18.4% (mean change +7.7%; p = 0.003). In non-smokers, progressive motility increased from 10.9 ± 9.6% to 12.8 ± 10.4% without reaching statistical significance (mean change +1.9%; p = 0.155), while normal morphology showed a statistically significant improvement from 25.1 ± 24.9% to 36.9 ± 20.3% (mean change +11.8%; p=0.003).

Baseline Demographic		Semen Parameter	Baseline Mean ± SD	Post Treatment Mean ± SD	Mean Change	P-value
Age Group (years)	2.5	Progressive motility (%)	10.6 ± 9.3	13.1 ± 10.5	+2.5	0.022
		Normal morphology (%)	24.8 ± 24.1	36.4 ± 20.7	+11.6	0.031
	>35	Progressive motility (%)	8.9 ± 8.7	10.0 ± 9.6	+1.1	0.285
		Normal morphology (%)	21.3 ± 22.2	30.1 ± 19.2	+8.8	0.031
Obesity Status	Obese	Sperm count (million/ml)	19.8 ± 21.7	21.1 ± 22.9	+1.3	0.64
		Normal morphology (%)	21.4 ± 21.6	29.6 ± 18.9	+8.2	0.002
	Non-obese	Sperm count (million/ml)	24.3 ± 24.6	26.8 ± 24.8	+2.5	0.415

		Normal morphology (%)	25.5 ± 24.8	38.7 ± 21.4	+13.2	0.002
Smoking Status	Smokers	Progressive motility (%)	8.1 ± 7.8	9.6 ± 8.9	+1.5	0.184
		Normal morphology (%)	20.1 ± 19.6	27.8 ± 18.4	+7.7	0.003
	Non-Smokers	Progressive motility (%)	10.9 ± 9.6	12.8 ± 10.4	+1.9	0.155
		Normal morphology (%)	25.1 ± 24.9	36.9 ± 20.3	+11.8	0.003

DISCUSSION

Idiopathic male subfertility represents a common yet diagnostically challenging condition in reproductive medicine, characterised by abnormal semen parameters in the absence of identifiable anatomical, endocrine, genetic, or infectious causes. The absence of a definitive aetiology often limits targeted management and necessitates reliance on empirical therapies. Among these, antioxidant supplementation has gained attention due to the well-established role of oxidative stress in sperm dysfunction and its potential reversibility. The present study therefore holds clinical relevance by evaluating changes in semen parameters following antioxidant therapy in a well-defined idiopathic subfertile population within a local tertiary care setting.

The study population comprised relatively young men with a mean age of 34.6±6.8 years and a moderate duration of subfertility, reflecting the typical demographic profile reported in idiopathic male infertility cohorts [1-3]. A substantial proportion of participants were obese and smokers, both of which are recognised contributors to oxidative stress and impaired spermatogenesis [12,16]. Baseline semen analysis demonstrated markedly reduced progressive motility and variable sperm morphology, consistent with oxidative stress-mediated sperm damage described in earlier studies [5-7]. These clinical and laboratory characteristics support the appropriateness of antioxidant therapy as a biologically plausible intervention in this cohort. Following three months of antioxidant supplementation, the most notable finding was a statistically significant improvement in normal sperm morphology, which increased from 23.22 ±

23.28% at baseline to 33.60 ± 20.01% post-treatment (p = 0.001). In contrast, changes in sperm volume, sperm concentration, and progressive motility did not achieve statistical significance. These results suggest that sperm morphology may be more responsive to antioxidant therapy than other conventional semen parameters, a pattern that has been reported previously. Sadaghiani et al. observed an approximate 10% absolute improvement in normal morphology following antioxidant supplementation in infertile male smokers, which is comparable to the 10.38 percentage point improvement observed in the present study [10]. Similarly, Ahmed et al. reported significant post-treatment improvements in morphology alongside modest, non-significant changes in sperm count and motility, supporting the selective sensitivity of morphology to oxidative stress modulation [11]. Systematic reviews and meta-analyses have also demonstrated heterogeneous effects of antioxidants on semen parameters. Li et al. reported consistent improvements in sperm morphology and motility across randomised controlled trials, although the magnitude of effect varied widely depending on antioxidant composition and treatment duration [4]. The Cochrane review by de Ligny et al. highlighted modest improvements in semen quality but emphasised uncertainty regarding clinical outcomes such as pregnancy rates, reinforcing the need for cautious interpretation of semen parameter changes [17]. The findings of the current study align with this body of evidence by demonstrating a statistically robust improvement in morphology without overstating effects on other parameters.

Stratified analysis further elucidated factors influencing treatment response. Younger participants (≤ 35 years) exhibited significant improvements in both progressive motility and morphology, whereas older participants showed improvement primarily in morphology. Age-related decline in mitochondrial efficiency and antioxidant defence capacity may attenuate the response of motility to therapy in older men, as suggested by previous mechanistic studies [6,9]. Obesity- and smoking-based stratification revealed significant improvements in morphology across all subgroups, although the magnitude of change was greater in non-obese and non-smoking participants. These findings are consistent with evidence linking obesity and smoking to increased seminal reactive oxygen species and reduced responsiveness to antioxidant therapy [12,15,16]. From a pathophysiological perspective, antioxidants may exert a greater effect on sperm morphology by reducing lipid peroxidation of sperm membranes and protecting spermatogenic cells during maturation, thereby improving structural integrity rather than immediately enhancing motility or concentration [5,13,18]. The lack of significant improvement in sperm count and volume may also reflect the relatively short intervention period, as these parameters are influenced by longer-term spermatogenic and endocrine factors. The strengths of this study include a clearly defined idiopathic subfertile population, standardised semen analysis using WHO criteria, and consistent pre- and post-treatment assessment. Additionally, the study contributes valuable local data from a public-sector tertiary care hospital, addressing a recognised gap in evidence from low- and middle-income settings [8,16]. However, several limitations must be acknowledged. The quasi-experimental design without a control group limits causal inference, and the single-centre setting with a modest sample size may restrict generalisability. Potential selection bias inherent to non-probability sampling cannot be excluded. Furthermore, oxidative stress markers and sperm DNA fragmentation indices were not assessed, which may have provided deeper mechanistic insight into treatment response [14,18,19].

The findings of the present study reinforce existing evidence that antioxidant supplementation is associated with a significant improvement in sperm morphology among men with idiopathic subfertility, while effects on other semen parameters appear limited. These results are consistent with prior clinical trials and systematic reviews and strengthen the evidence base supporting the role of antioxidants in addressing oxidative stress-related sperm dysfunction, particularly in resource-limited clinical settings.

CONCLUSION

Antioxidant supplementation administered for three months resulted in a statistically significant improvement in normal sperm morphology among men with idiopathic subfertility, whereas no significant changes were observed in sperm volume, sperm concentration, or progressive motility. These findings support a potential role for antioxidants in improving semen parameters associated with oxidative stress.

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